

Erratum: Social Media as an Early Crisis Communication Channel: A Virtual Ethnography of a Community Based Instagram Account During Flood and Landslide Disaster in the Gayo Highland Aceh

This erratum concerns the article published in Volume 8, No. 2, June 2026. Following formal galley proof approval by the authors and subsequent publication, an error was identified by the authors in the chronological metadata on the first page of the article. The submission date was erroneously printed as March 1, 2025.

To correct the chronological inconsistency regarding the December 2025 disaster event studied in the research, the timeline for the manuscript is officially amended as follows:

- **Correct Submission Date:** March 1, 2026

The online metadata on the journal website has been updated to reflect the correct submission year of 2026 to maintain historical accuracy. The text, data, and findings of the article remain unchanged.